

COMPONENT FATTY ACIDS OF MELON (*CUCUMIS MELO*, LINN). SEED OIL

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Component fatty acids of melon seed kernels consist of caproic (1.0%), caprylic (2.0%), myristic (1.1%) palmitic (7.3%), stearic (0.2%), oleic (43.1%) and linoleic acids (45.1%). Unsaponifiable matter in the oil is 0.9%.

Fully saturated glycerides are absent in the oil. Trilinolein does not exceed 1%, although 45.2% of linoleic acid are present in the mixed fatty acids. Thus acids are evenly distributed in the glycerides.

Kernels contain 40% oil, 22.7% proteins and 0.75% phosphates as P_2O_5 and can be used as a fairly good substitute for the more expensive almond seeds, as article of nutritive food.

The oil of seeds of melon or sweet melon (*Cucumis melo*, Linn), known in Hindustani Kharbuza, in Bengali Khurmuj, has been examined for the component fatty acids. The plant is an annual creeper and belongs to N. O. *Cucurbitaceae*. Melon fruit is grown abundantly all over India, and the seeds form a by-product. The seed kernels are used for edible purposes as substitute for more expensive nuts like almond kernels and pistachio kernels. The seeds are nutritive and are also used in India medicinally as lachrymatory, diuretic, for treatment of gonorrhoea and for curing painful discharge of urine.

The seed kernels contain a high percentage of oil (40%) and also contain a fairly high proportion of proteins (22.7%) and some phosphates (0.75% as P_2O_5). The present price of the melon kernels is about 33% of the almond kernels and considering their high nutritive value, they should form a fairly good substitute for the more expensive almonds and pistachio kernels, used as articles of rich and nourishing food. The oil obtained is also of a very fragrant smell, pleasant taste and can replace the more expensive almond oil valued for its high medicinal value. Melon seed oil is a semi-drying oil as seen by the data of the component fatty acids (oleic, 43.2% : linoleic, 45.2% ; caproic, 1.0% ; caprylic, 2.0% ; myristic 1.1% ; palmitic 7.3% ; stearic 0.2%). Unsaponifiable matter present in the oil is 0.9%. The composition of acids in the oil is in concordance with that of most of the other members of *Cucurbitaceae*, as shown by the generalisation of Hilditch (*Allgemeine Oel- u. Fett- Ztg.*, 1930, 27, 184, 219, 255). The composition of oil of melon seed from California given by Baughman and Jamieson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 152), given in Table IV, is somewhat different from that of the present oil, but total of unsaturated acids is almost similar. High percentage of oleic and linoleic acids is characteristic of this botanical family. Differences are due to a different origin of the seeds and also perhaps due to different species of *Cucumis melo*.

It has been observed in the case of several seeds that if the outer cover of the kernels is hard and tenacious, the seed fat is rich in saturated fatty acids but if otherwise, unsaturated acids predominate as component acids of glycerides as also shown by the present melon seed fat. Fully saturated glycerides are completely absent as expected, from the comparatively low percentage (11.6%) of saturated acids. Moreover, although 45.2% linoleic acid is present in the mixed acids, yet trilinolein does not exceed 1.0%.

Thus, there is even distribution of fatty acids in the glycerides and it supports the theory of even distribution of Hilditch (Collin and Hilditch, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 1273) in seed fats.

EXPERIMENTAL

The oil was extracted out of soft seed kernels from Punjab (India) seeds in a small press and it was clarified by filtration. The content of the oil in the kernels is 40% by ether extraction. The oil is bright pale-yellow in colour and possesses a pleasant smell and agreeable taste.

Some of the general characteristics of the oil, along with those of a few similar varieties are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Particulars	<i>Cucumis Melo</i> Linn (Indian)	<i>Cucumis Melo</i> L. (African) Fendler*	<i>Cucumis</i> <i>Sativus</i> (Indian) Hooper†	Melon seed oil (S. Russian) Lidoff. ‡
Yield of oil by extraction	40.0%	...	...	29.4%
Specific gravity	...	...	0.923-0.924	0.9276
Saponification value	207.4	193.3	195.2-196.9	190.5
Saponification equivalent	170.0	289.7	284.7-286.8	293.9
Acid Value	0.9	...	11.5	1.37
Iodine value	117.1	101.5	117.7-118.5	133.3
Unsaponifiable matter	0.79%	...	...	...

* Fendler, *Bull. Imp. Inst.* 1913, 56.

† Hooper, Annual Report. Indian Museum, 1907-1908, 13.

‡ J. Lewkowitsch, *Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes.*, Vol. II, (1922), p. 171.

Iodine value of the present oil is same as that of the melon seed oil examined by Hooper (*loc. cit.*) but saponification value is different. Low saponification value of the oil under examination is due to the presence of lower fatty acids. African and Russian oils are different from the Indian oil.

Examination of the Component Fatty Acids.—250 G. of the fat were saponified and the mixed acids separated into solid and liquid acids by lead salt-alcohol method. Each group of the acids was separately esterified to methyl esters and esters were fractionated under high vacuum of about 1 mm. Each fraction was separately examined and individual acids present were identified (Tables II and III)

TABLE II

Mixed fatty acids :—Saponification equivalent, 266.9, (calculated 267.4) ;
Iodine value, 120.6 (calculated 119.6).

		Corresponding Methyl esters.	
		Sap. equiv.	I.V.
Solid acids (S)	8.8%	267.0	1.80
Liquid Acids (L)	91.2%	267.4	124.2

TABLE III

(i) Methyl esters of "Liquid" (L) acids.									
No.	Wt.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.	No.	Wt.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.
L ₁	25.40 g.	148-177	259.1	128.4	L _{1a}	4.49	165-180	245.8	102.2
L ₂	8.53	174-179	264.2	127.0	L _{1b}	6.10	181-182	256.1	122.0
L ₃	8.44	181-183	168.5	127.8	L _{1c}	6.30	182	266.1	128.7
L ₄	6.92	183-190	270.9	129.5	L _{1d}	3.10	Residue	272.9	130.2
L ₅	4.78	195-208	276.1	130.4					
L ₆	15.20	Residue	281.0	132.9					
..	Acids-ex N.S (Found)		276.4	135.8					
..	Esters-ex N. S.								
	(Calculated)		290.4	129.2					

(ii) Methyl esters of "solid" (S) acids.				
No.	Wt.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.
S ₁	4.99 g.	160-167	262.3	1.40
S ₂	3.54	170-176	265.9	1.54
S ₃	3.80	178-188	267.4	2.10
S ₄	4.20	Residue	273.3	2.30

Identification of Acids.—Some of the ester fractions were hydrolysed and aqueous potassium salts of fatty acids were oxidised with alkaline permanganate solution. Unsaturated acids resulted in the production of hydroxy acids which were separated from the saturated acids by suitable solvents and were subjected to fractional crystallisation.

L_{1a} :—Dihydroxystearic acid (m. p. 129°) and tetrahydroxystearic acid (m. p. 174°) were isolated, showing the presence of $\Delta^9:10$ —oleic acid and $\Delta^9:10:12:13$ linoleic acid respectively.

L₂ :—The same acids as mentioned in L_{1a} fraction were confirmed.

S₁ :—Myristic acid (m. p. 54°) and palmitic acid (m. p. 62°) were identified.

S₄ :—The main acid in this fraction was palmitic acid (m. p. 62.5°) and stearic acid (m. p. 70°) was also separated.

From the above data, component fatty acids and unsaponifiable matter present in the oil were calculated and Table IV gives the percentage composition of these.

TABLE IV

Acids.	"Solid" acids 8.8%	"Liquid" acids 91.2%	Percentage of total fatty acids			Melon seed Banghamann & Jamieson (<i>loc. cit.</i>)
			Including N-S	Excluding N-S	Mols Rx N-S	
Caproic	...	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.3	...
Caprylic	...	2.0	2.0	2.0	3.7	...
Myristic	1.2	...	1.2	1.2	1.3	0.3
Palmitic	7.2	...	7.2	7.3	7.6	10.3
Stearic	0.2	...	0.2	0.2	0.2	4.6
Oleic	0.2	42.5	42.7	43.1	41.3	27.5
Linoleic	...	44.8	44.8	45.2	43.6	57.3
Unsaponifiable matter	...	0.9	0.9	...	...	...

Association ratio of mole of saturated to unsaturated acids is 1 : 5.62.

Glyceride Structure.—Oil (100 g.) was dissolved in acetone and kept at -5° for some days in a frigidaire. No solid separated, showing thereby the absence of fully saturated glycerides.

Bromination.—The oil (100 g.) was dissolved in petroleum ether ($40-60^{\circ}$) and brominated at -5° . Brominated glycerides were fractionally separated into several fractions by absolute alcohol, alcohol and acetone, and acetone etc. Alcohol-insoluble fraction corresponding to trilinolein was not more than 1% of the total.

Other fractions are being studied further.

Seed Analysis.

Kernels of the seed were extracted with ether and oil-free seed-cake was analysed for nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method and also for phosphorus. Proteins (22.7%) and phosphates (0.75% as P_2O_5) were thus found to be present in the kernels.

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